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EDITORIAL

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CURRICULUM AND STUDENTS' UNREST IN TERTIARY INSTITUTION: COUNSELLING IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Improving tertiary students' skills in obtaining adequate information about themselves and the environment is a problem that educators and counsellors must try to resolve. Some of the frustrating experiences for the students arise as a result of lack of self-knowledge as well of the environment. Students are confronted with many questions regarding their interests, abilities, aptitudes and intelligence generally. Hence, this paper foremost defined tertiary institutions. It went further to highlight the concepts of curriculum and counseling. Factors often associated with students' unrest were closely reviewed as well as the counseling implications. In other words. The role of counseling in mitigating the tendency for unrest in educational system was well highlighted. In the light of the above discussion, recommendations were made on how students should be assisted through the enrichment of curriculum planning among others to minimize students' unrest and violence in tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Curriculum, Students Unrest, Counseling.

Introduction

Student unrest has come to be regarded as a common occurrence. It takes form of either an orderly protest without violence: or disorderly protest involving disruption, violence and terrorism. Students have become concerned and involved in local, national and international issues in recent years as a means of winning a voice in policy matters affecting them and others. Many students are concerned not just with their immediate

adjustment, welfare and developmental problem, but also increasingly with the societal and environmental forces of influences which seem to impinge on them as members of the human race (Denga, 2010). He went on to say that they are also concerned with national and international peace. Many students today seek to participate actively and even aggressively in societal reconstruction and reformation, politically, and even violently, in order to try and change the societal norms. They are concerned not only with self but also with others as well. Thus, while one takes a hard look at students' violence, one should take cognizance of the positive motivation behind students' violence as well. It is only in this light that the problem of campus unrest can be appreciated. In a variety of relationship with students experiencing neurotic anxiety, worry, identity crisis, financial needs, conflating inter-personal relationships, career choice, and other bottlenecks to satisfaction and development, counselors must enter into a personalized and individualized assistance relationship to help students resolve these issues (Denga, 2012).

Nigeria tertiary educational institutions range from the universities to monotechnics including those institutions offering correspondence courses, (FRN,2013). The curricula of these institutions are established to attain the goals for which they are set up. The national policy on Education (FRN, 2013) went further to state that the goals of Nigerian tertiary institutions shall be:

- i. Contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower training.
- ii. Inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual society.
- iii. Develop the intellectual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate their local and external environments.
- iv. Acquire both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society.
- v. Promote and encourage scholarship and community service.
- vi. Forge and cement national unity.
- vii. Promote national and international understanding and interaction.

Concept of Curriculum

The word curriculum is a popular word in education literature. It is associated with education because of its relevance in achieving the educational objectives of any country. Once the aims, goals and objectives of education of any country are determined through identifying the needs, problems and aspirations of the country (needs analysis/situational analysis), these will be translated into an official document called the curriculum. This is done through the process curriculum planning and development which are quiet involving. In the light of this, curriculum can be defined as the totality of contents and learning experiences, planned and unplanned, offered to the learners under the guidance of the school for the learners' development in personal-social competence (Taba 1962 as cited by Duru (2016)).

Concept of Counselling

Counselling as a support and helping service is designed to provide an interaction where the counsellor attempts to help an individual improve himself either in his present or future decision or problem. Shertzer and Stone (1974), cited in Ogbodo (2017) define counselling as “an interaction process which facilitates meaningful understanding of self and environment and results in the establishment and/or clarification of goals and values for future behaviour. However, counselling as observed by Blocher, (1969) cited in Idowu, (2016), is helping an individual become more fully aware of himself and the ways in which he responds to the influence in his environment. It further helps him to establish some personal meaning for this behaviour and to develop and clarify a set goals and values for his future behaviour. As a proess, then, counselling is dynamic and educative in nature. Counsellor generally provides an atmosphere for realization of self-identity. She/he helps an individual to improve himself either in his present or future decisions or problems. It also involves a secure place where you and the counsellor are working together to clarify and develop a better understanding of your concerns, discover new strength within yourself, bring

forward new possibilities in the perception of your difficulties and help you make choice/change/decisions which are best for you.

According to Denga, (2012), the main purposes of students' counselling is the need for students' total development. Some of the central questions which counselling deals with include the extents to which students are growing in ability to cope with their own problems, and whether or not they are accomplishing that measure of self-realization which is necessary in reaching greater maturity. The basic objective of counselling generally is to help the individual to become independent and capable of operating on his own. Self-determination and self-clarification are possible only when personal insight has been achieved.

Student counselling is predicated on the belief that if students understand who they are, the nature and complexity of their problems and the rational means of resolving their issues, the present campus crises can be reduced. Freshmen appear to be plagued by the question of self-identity. Prior to university admission they were defined by their parents' status within the community, by their academic standing in secondary school and by their position within their peer group. Without these supports, many students feel stripped of their social identity. They need to redefine themselves not only academically where all the students are supposed to be bright, but they must also redefine themselves socially in order to gain acceptance into the new community.

Adjustment to the new environment for many fresh students is difficult and sometimes painful. One of the reasons why this adjustment is difficult is the gap that exists between life in the secondary school or place of work and life in the university. The gap persists in many areas, such as the size of the new institution, community traditions, values espoused by other students, course these differences often results in a crisis of some sort.

The objective of students counselling can be grouped into three main categories, According to Denga, (2012), these are:

- i. Educational counselling
- ii. Vocational counselling and

iii. Personal-social counselling

Educational counselling aims at providing for each student those learning experiences and opportunities that are best suited to be his interests, needs and abilities.

Vocational counselling aims at assisting the student to discover individual interests and aptitudes of which the student himself might not be aware of and to encourage and direct him to those occupational adjustments.

Goals of personal-social counselling include helping the individual to discover areas of major maladjustments, areas requiring establishment or re-establishment of more adequate experiences of treatment according to the needs of individual students.

Student Unrest and curriculum

One lasting way of curbing violent behaviour among the youth is to include some topics in the school curriculum which would work gradually on the minds and attitudes of the youth in a positive way. Preaching and counselling alone may not provide the entire answer to the fundamental problems of human agitation. The school curriculum should contain certain topics that focus on students' attitude and thinking process in order to bring about an easing of tension and anxieties that prompt unrest. The learning of moral values will certainly introduce constraints in the behaviour of students, and these constraints will go a long way towards reducing unruly behaviours.

Radical behaviour of youths more often represent a form of deviance from the established norms of a society or an organization. The sources of students' unrest as stated indicate a distance graphing between the needs of students and the satisfaction of those needs. University management may do their best in satisfying students' needs, but there is often a tendency on the part of the students to assert that adults are hypocritical, not realistic in their attempts to cater for the needs of students (Denga, 2012).

A return of subjects or topics where students would be taught virtues like truth, patience, compromise, conservation of resources, patriotism among others to the school curriculum is being advocated. The need for greater emphasis in social values through school curriculum is increasingly glaring in the light of the increasing rate of students' irrational behaviours. Disagreements between the youth and adults over the rules of behaviour, academic students, examination regulations, inter-personal relationship among males and females, students' methods of governing themselves and the like should not lead to the destruction of innocent lives and properties (Ogbod, 2017).

Williamson (Year?), cited in Denga, (2010) suggested several ways to ease out tension and find solutions to some of the unrest problems. His constructive suggestion needs amplification and modifications to suit the context of developing nations. The suggestions include the following:

- i. Students should be taught right from the primary school level how mankind has tried to solve his problems. The use of force has not always been the best solution, though wars of rebellion have been crushed with the use of force. Emphasis on the use of peaceful means to reach lasting solutions to problems at local and international levels will inculcate into the children some virtues of peaceful negotiations. History as a school subject is full of opportunities to inculcate moral values in students.
- ii. Students need to be exposed to some problems for which no solutions have been found. Mankind, not discouraged, is ever seeking better solutions to these problems without resorting to violence or abandoning his attempts. Youths need to derive consolation from the fact that there are several alternatives for mankind to try and resolve his issues. Patience, rationality, flexibility, compromise and sometimes better courses of action than clinging to a particular course of action as if it were the only solution to the situation. Educated people explore a variety of solutions to an issue before resorting to an action that might look brutal and vandalistic.
- iii. Political and cultural studies should cultivate the spirit of tolerance among the youths. Many cases of students' unrest occur as a result of a lack of tolerance of other people's political and religious ideologies. Students should be taught skills of give and take and to be broadminded

- enough to live and let live. Political and religious ethnocentrism should be discouraged among youth. Tolerance and accommodation of one another's behaviour in a diverse society such as Nigeria should be embedded in the curriculum.
- iv. Young people must be encouraged to do some social good in life. This means that each school child should be taught to be kind and helpful to others. He must assist the needy and exercise empathy for those who experience a feeling of low worth. An African is his brother's keeper. He must be caring and concerned about other people's plight.
 - v. Teachers and counselors must encourage students to hold debates, discussions and seminars on problem issues in the community. During these activities, rational solutions should be discussed. Those who hold radically different ideas could be made to learn more temperate methods of resolving problems even though they may not agree with the traditional and more gentle strategies of solving problems. Teachers and counsellors must not run away from discussing controversial issues in school as they often stick to the "safe" issues. Dealing with contentious issues in an intelligent, rational and constitutional way is far better than in an emotional, turbulent and radical manner.
 - vi. Students can be encouraged during essay writing periods in English class to think and develop arguments in writing for or against certain actions taken by the government. Thus, they can develop systematic argument in favour of or against the government's political decisions without resorting to physical confrontation with the government over policy issues. Rational in-depth arguments rather than impulsive reactions should be encouraged among students.

Counselling Implications

Counselling as a personal interaction with an individual and a helping profession, the students must be encouraged to adopt self-control techniques in the tertiary institutions. The notion of self-control is often associated with the ideals of freedom and self-improvement. A free person is one who guides, directs and controls his actions. He is a master of himself and his

environment. A mark of a “civilized” society is the degree to which its inhabitants can direct, maintain, and coordinate their behaviour without external coercion. Setting out to inculcate the right values, ethic and adopt peaceful ways of resolving one’s issues and being rational are some of the ways in which a person can regulate his behaviour. If are embedded in the curriculum right from the primary school level, it will be possible for counsellors and lecturers to encourage students of tertiary institutions to develop them the right values.

Conclusion

It can be concluded therefore, that students in tertiary institutions needs a social and moral renewal. The starting point is the curriculum. Students should be taught how to solve problems without resorting to violence. The youth must be socialized through the internalization of moral values and rational processes of tackling issues that threaten their welfare.

Curriculum renewal aimed at addressing the issue of student unrest need not be construed to mean purging the existing system to establish something new and radically different. This would neither be productive nor desirable. The present move towards curriculum expansion to include the social and moral aspects is a gradual process. Change threatens the existing status quo and the best way to effect it is to adopt a selective, gradual and persuasive procedure. Making curriculum planners responsive to the needs of today’s youths will certainly help reduce the incidence of unrest and other forms of turbulent behaviours in tertiary institutions.

Recommendation

Base on the discussions so far, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The curriculum is an important starting point to develop academic and social programmes that will response to students’ unrest. Hence the planner should take into consideration all the social vices that will affect the youths in future.

- ii. The curriculum should involve in all the values clarification embedded in human being such as patriotism, dedication, diligent, habit of living in peace with one another.
- iii. The counsellor should always update themselves through learning by attending conferences, workshop, and seminars to improve their knowledge in other to help students avoid problems that lead to unrest.
- iv. Group counselling will be of great benefit in assisting students to problems are involved, individual counselling should be preferred.
- v. The government and the tertiary institutions management should make the learning environment more conducive for students' to cope with their studies.

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